

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND EDUCATION

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Research always provides vast knowledge with scientific approach and educational research provides current approaches along with implication in teaching learning process. We distribute knowledge in verity of discipline for making structure storage each discipline provide much specific information about a particular concept and while going to apply that knowledge in education we find that each and every discipline is interdependent. While we use particular concept with combination of discipline we find that is helpful for concept formation and better understanding of students. Educational researchers have experience that development of students depends on fulfilment of all kind of objective like...

1. Cognitive

2. Affective

3. Psychomotor

For that researcher must have to know that interdisciplinary research is needed to getting better result.

Key words:- Discipline, Interdisciplinary research.

Discipline:-

This term refers to a specific body of knowledge with its own background of education, training, procedures, methods and content areas.

Hope,1995

Discipline is a collection of related activities that are related to a major 'area of concern' within overall project. The grouping activities into disciplines are mainly an aid to understanding the project from a 'traditional' waterfall perspective- typically.

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Due to the explosion of knowledge different types of disciplines existed but this all disciplines are co related and always provide co operation in development of various fields.

Interdisciplinary research:-

Interdisciplinary research is a mode of research by team's or individuals that integrates information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts and theories from two or more discipline or bodies of specialized knowledge to advance fundamental understanding or to solve problems whose solutions are beyond the scope of a single discipline or area of research practice.

National academy of science.

These are defined as a project that involve several unrelated academic disciplinary in a way that forces them to cross subject boundaries to create new knowledge and theory and solve common research goal. By unrelated it is meant that they have contrasting research paradigm.

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It all mean that interdisciplinary research have collaboration of two disciplines for getting best outcome. Interdisciplinary research gives large scope for researcher to think on a concept to solve it researcher mix his methodology with relative discipline.

USE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH IN EDUCATION

Foundation of interdisciplinary techniques will lead to a future of disciplinary innovation. Interdisciplinary approach has become an important and challenging technique in the modern curriculum.

- 1) Co-relation studies in educational research needed interdisciplinary approach Example. Job satisfaction of teacher and students achievement. These types of research helpful for principle development in education.
- 2) Basically education process is interdependent and inter related with management, administration, psychology because of that interdisciplinary research always important to solve educational problems.
- 3) Medium of instruction in school level, quality improvement and quality assurance in schools and colleges. This type of subjects must need interdisciplinary research.
- 4) Educational science is integration of many disciplines because of that the interdisciplinary research are needed in it.
- 5) Interdisciplinary research is combination of knowledge of many disciplines for wide aspects and objective of this kind of research is to solve problem and for this exchange of knowledge is needed and beneficial for educational development.

For above mentioned use of interdisciplinary research in education is always provide opportunity to exchange knowledge within discipline for batter education. Main objective of education is to help student's all-round development and interdisciplinary research exploding knowledge which helps each and every teacher to know combination of subjects, concepts.

Interdisciplinary research and Future education:-

- 1) If we provide facility to students learn many discipline at a time they get more knowledge in one academic year and it bust our educational system so we must see interdisciplinary research and interdisciplinary education is future of our education.
- 2) We provide foundation of interdisciplinary techniques to our student's they will get lead world wide discovery and innovations.
- 3) Interdisciplinary research prepares wide aspect of students about knowledge which help them for batter future.

This paper focus on benefits of interdisciplinary research in our educational system and it make positive changes which help our students to become global citizen. Interdisciplinary makes our students as a member of knowledge society for knowledge construction and application. To get all that benefits we reconstruct Indian educational policy for adaptation of interdisciplinary approach.

Reference:-

<http://dc.cod.edu/essai/vol7/iss1/26>

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